

AMR IN AGRIFOOD TRANSDISCIPLINARY NETWORK

27-28 NOVEMBER 2024

LAUNCH MEETING REPORT & STRATEGIC ROADMAP

UK Research
and Innovation

THE AMAST, A UKRI NETWORK

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a critical and often overlooked risk to our food, crops and livestock. This risk increases the potential for both human disease and its treatment, and loss of income for farmers, grocers and other members of the supply chain within the agrifood sector. In addition to intrinsically resistant microorganisms, antimicrobial resistance arises from naturally occurring microbes present in foods, crops and animals which have acquired genetic mutation(s) or other means of resisting antimicrobials used to treat human and animal disease. This acquisition of drug resistance has profound impact on our health services where previously treatable infections become resistant to one or more antimicrobials.

This challenge needs to be addressed by coordinated work between those with roles in disease prevention and the use of antimicrobials together with those in academia, food production and policy makers. It is only by taking a whole system approach to this difficult challenge that we will develop mitigations. Some success has already been seen in the UK with the reduction and selective use of antimicrobials in agrifood settings.

The AMAST (Antimicrobial Resistance in Agrifood Systems Transdisciplinary) Network Launch Meeting marked a significant milestone in the UK's fight against AMR, bringing together key agrifood stakeholders to establish a comprehensive research framework for addressing AMR from a farm-to-fork perspective. As one of eight UK AMR networks funded by UKRI, recognising that risks of resistance need to be considered across domains of human, animal, food, plant and ecosystems health, AMAST has received initial funding of £650,000, including a £162,000 flexible fund for Phase 1, with potential access to part of a £7 million commitment across networks for Phase 2. With these resources, and importantly, with the cross-sectoral collaboration within the network, AMAST will inject a powerful and informed new voice for agrifood stakeholders into the discussion of AMR in the UK.

The AMAST launch meeting established the foundation for a transdisciplinary approach to tackling AMR challenges in the agrifood sector, emphasizing the importance of collaborative action and evidence-based solutions. The two-day event, held in person at the Kia Oval in London on 27-28 November 2024, brought together 30 participants from across the agrifood sector and health sector, including 16 representatives from AMAST partner organisations. The participant mix reflected the transdisciplinary and trans-sectoral nature of the AMAST Network, seeking to collectivise the expertise from industry representatives, research institutions, government bodies, public and veterinary healthcare sector representatives, and with participants sharing experiences from international activities.

The meeting format combined structured presentations with intensive breakout discussion sessions, allowing for active engagement and meaningful dialogue between diverse stakeholders. Sessions were facilitated to ensure all voices were heard and diverse perspectives were captured, leading to practical recommendations for the network's development, clear identification of priorities, and establishment of relationships across sectors that will be crucial for success of the AMAST network.

NETWORK OVERVIEW AND CONTEXT

AMAST's primary mission centres on understanding and tackling AMR through a comprehensive farm-to-fork perspective, creating a transdisciplinary network that effectively connects researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. The network's explicit alignment with the UK's National Action Plan on AMR (2024 to 2029), positions it to be a crucial contributor to the UK's broader AMR strategy.

The network's funding structure has been designed to underpin its ambitious goals and to support the inclusion and activities of the AMAST membership, including those representing animal and crop production sectors. The total Phase 1 funding of £650,000 has been strategically allocated across various essential activities. This includes a substantial flexible fund of £162,000 designated to achieve core network objectives, £80,000 for community meetings, £45,000 for workshops, and £25,000 for communication support. This approach ensures resources are available for both planned activities and emerging opportunities brought forward by AMAST members.

PRESENTATIONS SUMMARY

AMAST partners provided plenary materials on their perspectives and ongoing activities relating to addressing the AMR challenge.

Each presentation served to set the scene for facilitated breakout group discussions:

- to gather partner feedback (see Appendixes) on urgent AMR research priorities,
- to discuss best practice to define and communicate AMR priorities,
- to identify existing resources amongst the partners and stakeholders
- to form the AMAST stakeholder engagement strategy.

Matt Gilmour from the Quadram Institute, **K. Marie McIntyre** from Newcastle University and AMAST leadership team opened the event by welcoming all partners and describing the growing opportunity to solve/mitigate the complex threat of AMR by connecting the UK's great expertise in agriculture and sciences. The AMAST vision was reiterated – to develop connected research pathways facilitating understanding of the challenges and opportunities for mitigating the emergence and transmission of AMR through agrifood systems – as were the network objectives, scope and the membership of full leadership team and core partners. Parallels were drawn with other established frameworks where One Health interventions are designed by defining the problem, bringing together the involved actors, describing the system we seek to change, and then developing pathways towards intervention through transdisciplinary working.

Laura Higham from FAI (Food Animal Initiative) Farms presented insights from working with major food retailers, demonstrating the intricate relationship between meeting welfare standards and prudent antimicrobial usage. Her presentation emphasised the importance of balanced scoring systems for sustainability and advocated for a One Health approach that recognises the complexities of interconnections between human, animal, and environmental health.

Rodolphe Mader from the International Centre for Antimicrobial Resistance Solutions (ICARS) brought an international perspective, sharing experiences from implementing AMR intervention projects in developing countries. His presentation of successful case studies, particularly the Farmer Field Schools initiative, highlighted the importance of meaningful governmental engagement and multi-stakeholder approaches to achieve sustainable and lasting outcomes.

Mandy Nevel from the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) provided insights into the global context of AMR challenges, particularly focusing on accessibility of antimicrobials outside the UK and post-Brexit implications for vaccine licensing. Her presentation emphasised the critical need for improved animal health across all sectors and the importance of coordinated action in addressing AMR challenges. She also mentioned the potential of bacteriophages as an alternative approach to tackle AMR and reduce reliance on antibiotics.

Sharon Pfleger from NHS Highland brought a public health perspective, providing sobering statistics on AMR mortality rates and discussing the significant challenges in the development of new antibiotics. Her presentation connected AMR to broader health determinants, emphasising the need for a comprehensive approach to addressing this global challenge.

CRITICAL CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED

The launch meeting revealed several interconnected challenges that must be addressed for effective strategies and policies to mitigate AMR.

In terms of technical challenges, the network identified the fundamental need for standardisation of AMR definitions, measurements, and terminology across sectors. Recent progress has been made with the Advisory Committee on the Microbiological Safety of Food recommending standardised AMR terminology, but further work is needed. While AMR definitions themselves are well-established between animal and human health sectors, the primary challenge lies in the lack of harmonised clinical breakpoints and interpretive criteria. This leads to situations where different laboratories may use varying interpretation criteria when determining whether an isolate is resistant to a specific antibiotic, resulting in inconsistent reporting of resistance patterns even when testing the same isolate. This lack of harmonisation between laboratories presents a significant barrier to consistent data collection, analysis, and development of standardised interpretive criteria for susceptibility testing and relationships to genotypes. Moreover, data sharing and privacy concerns emerged as critical issues, particularly regarding farmer confidentiality and commercial sensitivity. The integration of various surveillance systems, while necessary, presents complex technical and organisational challenges that require careful consideration.

The slow pace and complexity of regulatory progress emerged as a fundamental challenge, particularly in the post-Brexit context. This regulatory “inertia” affects multiple areas, from vaccine licensing to the approval of antibiotic alternatives that could help reduce antimicrobial usage. The limited availability of vaccines licensed for use by other partner nations is one consequence.

Planning permission for farm infrastructure improvements and the alignment of environmental regulations with practical farming needs were identified as significant obstacles to implementing better AMR management practices. The situation is further complicated by promising alternative treatments remaining in regulatory limbo, despite their potential to decrease reliance on antibiotics. The international trade implications of AMR management practices add another layer of complexity to the regulatory landscape, with particular concerns about the lack of AMR surveillance in imported foods - although the FSA aims to address this in the coming financial year, as highlighted in the Society for Applied Microbiology's report on food safety after Brexit (November 2018).

Key challenges in AMR Management

All challenges require coordinated cross-sector responses for effective AMR management

Please see [Appendix 3 – Prioritising AMR Research](#) for further specific information collected during breakout discussions

Implementation challenges varied significantly across different agricultural sectors. The engagement of farmers requires sector-specific approaches that acknowledge the varying levels of systematic antimicrobial use monitoring already in place - for example, poultry, pig, and aquaculture (particularly salmon) sectors have established structured systems for voluntary data collection and antimicrobial stewardship, while other sectors have different approaches and monitoring frameworks that need to be considered in engagement strategies. Resource constraints, particularly in terms of time and labour, present significant barriers to adoption of new practices. Barriers exist between academic research and on-farm adoption, including both knowledge transfer challenges and insufficient field-based evidence to support the implementation of interventions, requiring innovative solutions for effective communication and behaviour change as well as increased investment in practical trials that demonstrate real-world efficacy and economic viability.

STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS

The stakeholder landscape identified by AMAST is complex and multifaceted, encompassing a wide range of actors across the agrifood sector. Primary stakeholders include farmers across agriculture, horticulture, and livestock sectors - spanning crop producers, horticulturalists, and animal producers - whose engagement is crucial and requires different approaches depending on their specific production systems. Veterinarians play a pivotal role as practitioners and guardians of responsible antimicrobial use (AMU), providing crucial on-the-ground implementation of stewardship practices and direct engagement with farmers. Separately, retailers and food producers/processors, while having significant influence over supply chain practices through their individual requirements, present distinct engagement challenges and often require different approaches to secure their participation in AMR initiatives. Regulators and policymakers shape the framework within which AMR management occurs, and the research community provides the evidence base for decision-making and policy development.

The support network for these primary stakeholders is equally important, comprising industry bodies which provide crucial links to their members through diverse means. Professional organisations offer technical expertise and training, while academic institutions contribute research capabilities including for emerging methods and practices, and educational resources. International partners bring valuable external perspectives and opportunities for valuable knowledge exchange, although Brexit has introduced new complexities to these relationships.

Please see [Appendix 2 - Mapping Resources and Expertise](#) for further specific information collected during breakout discussions

RESOURCE ANALYSIS

Existing data repositories, such as the Electronic Medicine Book for pigs (eMB-Pigs), the Medicine Hub for ruminants, PATH-SAFE datasets, and APHA genomic database, each provide valuable baseline data and monitoring capabilities. Research facilities, including the Mesocosm Facility at Fera and UK Agri-Tech Centre, offer opportunities for the integration of controlled studies and practical demonstrations. Industry networks and technical expertise across various sectors provide essential knowledge and implementation capabilities.

However, significant resource gaps exist that need to be addressed. The lack of integrated surveillance systems hampers comprehensive monitoring of AMR trends, while variations in testing methods between laboratories and breakpoint definitions make data comparison challenging. The absence of coordinated and secure data sharing platforms with agreed sharing protocols limits the potential for cross-sector learning, and communication infrastructure needs strengthening to support effective knowledge transfer across the network.

There are also technical knowledge gaps on AMU, including the reasons for antimicrobial use in animals, relationship between AMU and AMR, and basic animal husbandry and nutrition support (impact of management practices, role of nutrition in reducing need for AMU, prevention strategies).

It is worth noting that the UK does have good estimates of antimicrobial usage quantities by animal species, which are reported annually in the Veterinary Antimicrobial Resistance and Sales Surveillance (VARSS) report. The VARSS data monitoring programmes are commissioned and funded by the VMD; data for the sales section are produced by the VMD and data for the antibiotic resistance section are produced and collated by APHA.

Please see [Appendix 4 - Expanding the Network](#) for further specific information collected during breakout discussions

PROPOSED STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK

The proposed strategic framework for AMAST aims to address the complex challenges of AMR while maximising the potential of available resources and networked partnerships.

Five fundamental pillars will guide the network's activities.

1. Knowledge Building and Sharing, to ensure that research findings and best practices are disseminated effectively across the network.
2. Stakeholder Engagement and Communication, to facilitate meaningful dialogue and collaboration between sectors.
3. Research and Innovation, to drive the development of new solutions and approaches, with methods facilitating cross-sector collaboration.
4. Policy Influence and Regulatory Alignment, to ensure that research findings translate into practical changes.
5. Cross Network and International Collaboration, to position AMAST within the global fight against AMR.

These core pillars are strengthened by cross-cutting themes that reflect broader societal concerns and opportunities:

1. One Health – human, animal, plant and ecosystems health are interconnected.
2. Sustainability – ensuring that proposed solutions are not only viable in the long term but also meet environmental, economic, social, animal welfare and human sustainability criteria.
3. Economic viability for farmers and other stakeholders – factoring individual farm economics, time and resource implications, Return on Investment (ROI) calculations / barriers to implementation of new practices.
4. Social responsibility underlies all activities – AMR management has broad societal implications that require full consideration.

KNOWLEDGE BUILDING AND SHARING

This pillar involves the development of a centralised knowledge repository, regular research syntheses, and practical guidance documents. This will include the creation of case studies showing successful interventions, a database of best practices, and regular knowledge-sharing events that bring together diverse stakeholders to exchange experiences and insights.

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND COMMUNICATION

Sector-specific working groups (for example, industry meetings hosted with pig, ruminant and crop producers that involve researchers), regular consultative forums for cross-sector working, and targeted communication channels for different stakeholder groups. The network will establish a regular presence at key industry events, develop sector-specific communication materials (with accessible, clear messaging and a defined direction), and create platforms for ongoing dialogue between researchers, practitioners, and policymakers.

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Address identified knowledge gaps through coordinated research initiatives. Priority areas include understanding transmission pathways, co-selection of AMR by other compounds (e.g. heavy metals and specific categories of pesticides), developing practical interventions for different farming sectors that consider behaviour change, and evaluating the economic impacts of AMR management strategies. Innovation will be encouraged through targeted funding calls, collaborative research projects, and support for practical on-farm trials. Engagement with Innovate UK could help drive the interface between research and industry.

POLICY INFLUENCE AND REGULATORY ALIGNMENT

Activities will include parallel engagement streams: direct work with policymakers through evidence-based policy briefs and participation in government consultations, alongside strategic engagement with politicians and parliamentarians to build awareness and support for AMR initiatives. The latter will include building relationships with key parliamentary champions and relevant select committees to ensure AMR remains high on the political agenda. The network will establish a policy working group to coordinate responses to regulatory proposals and actively contribute to supporting delivery of the National Action Plan, whilst providing a vehicle to garner political support for key network goals.

CROSS NETWORK AND INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

Knowledge exchange partnerships, joint research initiatives, and participation in global AMR forums. This will include regular interaction with similar networks in other countries, participation in international research projects, and contribution to global AMR reduction initiatives.

IMPLEMENTATION ROADMAP

The success of AMAST depends on actionable recommendations that can be implemented across different timeframes.

IMMEDIATE ACTIONS (FIRST 6 MONTHS)

The network establishes its operational foundation. This includes forming working groups that are inclusive of all agrifood sectors, while developing comprehensive terms of reference for the working groups and establishing transparent decision-making processes. The communication strategy will be developed with input from all stakeholder groups, ensuring appropriate channels and messages for different audiences. The stakeholder engagement programme needs clear objectives, research priorities, measurable outcomes, and dedicated resources for implementation.

MEDIUM-TERM PRIORITIES (6-18 MONTHS)

Research collaborations will be developed through formal partnership agreements, with specific objectives and aligned resource commitments. The AMAST Flexible Fund will be deployed amongst the membership to respond to research and training needs (e.g., short-term exchanges; visits or workshops at different facilities), as identified by the working groups. The policy influence strategy will be based on robust evidence and strong stakeholder relationships. International partnerships will be cultivated through formal agreements and joint projects. The funding model will explore diverse additional revenue streams, including industry partnerships, research grants, and service provision.

LONG-TERM GOALS (18+ MONTHS)

The transformation of AMR management in the agrifood sector requires sustained effort and resource commitment. This includes (where not already existing) developing centres of excellence, establishing best practice demonstration sites, and creating sustainable knowledge transfer mechanisms. The UK's leadership in AMR mitigation will be demonstrated, through AMAST and the other networks, through measurable outcomes, influential research, and effective policy frameworks that align with and support delivery of the National Action Plan for AMR.

SUCCESS METRICS AND EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

SUCCESS METRICS HAVE BEEN DESIGNED TO CAPTURE BOTH QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE ASPECTS OF AMAST'S IMPACT.

Quantitative metrics will track concrete outcomes such as stakeholder engagement levels, research outputs, and knowledge transfer activities. These will be complemented by measures of policy influence and practical implementation of AMR management strategies. This evaluation framework takes into account the importance of measuring not just activities but their actual impact on AMR management practices, recognising that attributing direct impact to AMAST activities will sometimes be challenging.

Qualitative indicators will assess the less tangible but equally important aspects of the network's effectiveness. These include the quality of stakeholder relationships, the practical application of knowledge gained through the network, and evidence of behavioural change among key stakeholders. Regular evaluation against these metrics will ensure the network remains focused on its objectives while allowing for adaptation to emerging challenges and opportunities.

It is worth noting that Early Career Researcher development and training will be central to the AMAST activities. We will deploy the AMAST Flexible Fund to organise Short Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) that train early career researchers (ECRs) in priority areas identified by the network. These STSMs will generate seed corn data that will provide evidence base for larger grant applications to sustain AMAST operations beyond Phase 1.

All our activities will consider Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) principles to ensure equitable access and development for the next generation of AMR researchers.

NETWORK EFFECTIVENESS METRICS

- Membership growth and diversity of participation
- Quality and frequency of interactions
- Resource utilisation and efficiency, including coordination with other AMR networks to maximise resources and avoid duplication

RESEARCH IMPACT MEASURES

- Number of peer-reviewed and other research outputs
- Implementation of research findings
- Citations and academic impact
- Practical application of research demonstrated through impact case studies

STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT INDICATORS

- Participation and engagement levels across different stakeholder groups in network activities
- Stakeholder satisfaction levels
- Cross-sector collaboration instances

POLICY INFLUENCE METRICS

- Policy changes attributed to network activities
- Engagement with policymakers
- Citations in policy documents
- Regulatory improvements achieved

IMPLEMENTATION SUCCESS MEASURES

- Adoption of recommended practices
- Changes in antimicrobial usage patterns
- Economic impacts on stakeholders
- Improved environmental outcomes
- Improved animal health and welfare

APPENDIX 1 - MEETING AGENDA

AMAST Network Launch

27-28 November 2024

Venue: The Kia Oval, London

Address: THE KIA OVAL
Surrey County Cricket Club
Kennington, London, SE11 5SS
The Pakistan Room

Invitees: AMAST Leadership Team and Core Partners

Objectives:

- 1. Introduce and contextualise the AMAST Network**
 - a. Purpose, structure, and objectives. AMAST's role within the broader landscape of AMR research and policy
 - b. Relationships with UKRI and other Transdisciplinary Networks
 - c. Discuss the NAP on AMR and its relevance to agrifood systems
- 2. Start building a transdisciplinary community that is central to the AMAST's mission**
 - a. Initialise the AMAST community through priority setting and opening dialogue to allow and co-creation and development between the AMAST leadership team and core AMAST partners
 - b. Facilitate connections between diverse partners from academia, industry, policy, and consumer groups
 - c. Encourage knowledge exchange across different sectors of the agrifood system
 - d. Identify Existing connections within the network
 - e. Explore best practices for achieving effective transdisciplinary collaboration
- 3. Begin the work of identifying and prioritising AMR challenges in agrifood sector**
 - a. Begin to develop a shared understanding of the complex AMR landscape in the UK agrifood sector
 - b. Begin to collectively identify key AMR issues and prioritise research and intervention points in UK agrifood systems from farm-to fork
 - c. Discuss types of outputs that would be helpful, aligned with available budget and potential for leveraging additional support
- 4. Actively engage partners in shaping the network's development and activities**
 - a. Gather input on network's potential value and impact from diverse perspectives
 - b. Identify additional partners and resources to incorporate into the network
 - c. Discuss strategies for ongoing community engagement and knowledge exchange
 - d. Capture existing, forthcoming, and anticipated activities related to AMR in agrifood systems
- 5. Advance the planning for core AMAST objectives (e.g. stakeholder interviews and mapping)**
 - a. Outline next steps and upcoming opportunities for network involvement
 - b. Set the stage for future collaborative projects, including stakeholder interviews
 - c. Generate enthusiasm and commitment for active participation in the AMAST Network

Agenda

27 November 2024

- 13:30 – 14:00** **Arrival & informal networking over coffee/tea/snacks**
- 14:00 – 14:30** **AMAST Introduction**
- Overview of AMAST's purpose, structure and goals.
 - Definition of what we mean as a network by interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary.
 - Brief overview of the NAP on AMR and its relevance to agrifood systems
- 14:30 – 15:00** **AMAST in context: Relationships and Collaborations**
- UKRI: Funding Landscape and expectations
 - Microbiology Society: collaborative opportunities
 - Other Transdisciplinary Networks: brief introduction
 - Aligning AMAST with existing initiatives and leveraging support
- 15:00 – 15:30** **FAI Farms/Vet Sustain perspective on AMR – Laura Higham (FAI Farms Veterinary Consultant & Founder and Director of Vet Sustain)**
Q/A and discussion time
- 15:30 – 15:45** **Coffee break**
- 15:45-16:30** **Breakout discussion – Realising AMAST's potential**
- Value and potential of the AMAST Network
 - Focus on identifying key AMR issues in agrifood systems
 - Mapping existing connections within the network
- 16:30 – 17:00** **ICARS' perspective on AMR – Rodolphe Mader (science Advisor at The International Centre for Antimicrobial Resistance Solutions - ICARS)**
Q/A and discussion time
- 17:00 – 17:45** **Breakout discussion – Mapping Existing Resources and Expertise**
- Identify existing resources and areas for collaboration
 - Discussion on integrating diverse expertise across the network
 - Capture forthcoming or anticipated activities related to AMR in agrifood
- 17:45 – 18:00** **Day 1 closure – Brief recap of key points and preview of Day 2**

28 November 2024

- 9:00 – 9:30** **Day 1 Recap**
- 9:30 – 10:00** **AHDB's perspective – Mandy Nevel (Head of Animal Health and Welfare at Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board - AHDB)**
Q/A and discussion time
- 10:00 – 10:45** **Breakout discussion – Prioritising AMR Research (issues that are worth investigating/addressing)**
- Discuss and prioritise AMR problems for investigation
 - Alignment with AMAST objectives and community needs
 - Criteria for prioritisation
- 10:45 – 11:00** **Coffee break**
- 11:00 – 11:30** **NHS Highland's perspective – Sharon Pflieger (Consultant in Pharmaceutical Public Health for NHS Highland)**
Q/A and discussion time
- 11:30 – 12:15** **Breakout discussion – Expanding the Network**
- Identify potential partners and stakeholders to engage
 - Strategies for inclusive representation across the agrifood system
- 12:15 – 13:30** **Lunch**

13:30 – 14:15 Breakout discussion – Engagement and Knowledge Exchange
- Discussion on interview processes and community engagement
- Strategies for effective knowledge exchange across disciplines
- Best practices for achieving effective transdisciplinary collaboration

14:15 – 15:00 Closing Remarks and Next Steps
- Summary of key outcomes and action items
- Preview of upcoming AMAST activities and opportunities for involvement
- Brief discussion on meeting effectiveness and next steps for the network
- Post-event survey

APPENDIX 2 - MAPPING RESOURCES AND EXPERTISE

EXISTING DATA RESOURCES AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Established databases:

- [eMB \(pigs\)](#): industry-led medicine recording with benchmarking
- [Medicine Hub](#) (ruminants): centralised but voluntary system
- APHA genomic data: pathogen surveillance, resistance organisms
- [PATH-SAFE](#): cross-sector dataset integration
- [DEFRA pesticide survey](#): includes fungicide usage
- FAI databases: commercial supply chain data
- ICARS [knowledge hub](#)
- [Enterobase](#) (with noted limitations in metadata and upload frequency)

Research resources and facilities:

- [Mesocosm Facility](#) at Fera: experimental system
- [UK Agri-Tech Centre](#): technology testing network
- Wastewater surveillance 2025 initiative – water treatment and wetland facilities
- Academic research capabilities
- Industry research facilities

Social sciences resources

Existing literature on farm behaviour patterns, decision-making processes, risk perceptions, prescribing practices, usage patterns, marketing and consumer behaviour.

DATA MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES

Confidentiality and trust

Legal requirements for farmer consent, protection from NGO targeting, commercial sensitivity, need for secure sharing protocols, trust-building mechanisms required.

Technical integration

Laboratory harmonisation needed, standardisation of methods across sectors, cross-border data sharing, cost implications of testing location.

KNOWLEDGE GAPS IDENTIFIED

Technical understanding

AMU quantification accuracy, relationship between use and resistance, basic husbandry impact, environmental transmission pathways, impact of heavy metals, other pollutants (e.g. pesticides and microplastics) and natural antimicrobials on AMR, contribution of AMR in food (including across different sections of the farm to fork food system) on emerging resistance in people compared to other sources, for international food production, which regulatory guidelines are followed (within production country or UK) and the impact of this upon transmission.

Behavioural aspects

Information processing patterns, risk perception factors, decision-making drivers.

Implementation challenges

Time constraint vs economic benefits, labour availability impact, practical barriers to change.

Surveillance

Public-private lab integration, method standardisation, cross-border coordination, environmental monitoring.

INTEGRATION STRATEGIES

Stakeholder alignment

Start with identifying shared priorities, focus on common viewpoints before addressing differences, use of qualified facilitators with cross-disciplinary experience, creation of open discussion spaces.

Implementation

One Health approach integration, disciplinary perspective combination, trade-off management, farm-specific/field-specific analysis (including economic argument), systems perspective and approaches where needed.

UPCOMING INITIATIVES

Policy developments

DEFRA mandatory medicine recording, animal health pathway, suitable qualified professionals prescribing legislation.

Industry events calendar

Sector-specific meetings, cross-sector opportunities, international connections, knowledge exchange forums. This includes poultry sector meetings, sheep and dairy sector events, crop events, Groundswell.

Recruitment and affiliation

Continuing identification of organizations, interest groups and constituencies to build capacity for information sharing, networking and horizon scanning.

RESOURCE SHARING FRAMEWORK

Data management

Equitable access protocols, sensitive information protection, source integration methods, collection standardisation.

Best practices

Benchmarking systems, usage policies, plant and soil health integration, cross-sector protocols.

APPENDIX 3 - PRIORITISING AMR RESEARCH

PRIORITY AREAS

Environmental and Transmission Research

- Identification of AMR pathogen reservoirs in UK
- Understanding farm entry and exit points for AMR pathogens
- Impact of manure use in environment – specific concern about poultry litter use in soil due to fertiliser process (need for assessment of AMR increase risk)
- Understanding transmission dynamics and pathways: direction and strength of transmission routes and impact assessment methodology
- Antibiotics and antifungal use in crop disease management and its contribution to AMR

Surveillance and Monitoring

Current gaps include: fragmented veterinary laboratory data, loss of data sent to EU labs, lack of coordinated AMR surveillance, need for imported food monitoring and assessment of AMR risks in trade movements.

Sector-Specific Priorities

- Poultry: *Campylobacter* increasingly becoming resistant to fluoroquinolones. Need for industry council engagement (BPC, BEIC)
- Cattle/Sheep: mastitis issues, lameness problems, respiratory diseases
- Dairy: transition from prophylactic use, drug withdrawal period impact

Policy, legal and regulatory analysis

- Understanding the current framework within which government, constituency groups and regulators operate
- Map policy, legal and regulatory practice to AMAST network goals

Alternatives to Antimicrobials

- Investigation of bacteriophages as therapeutic alternatives, building on extensive research from places like Georgia
- Research into CRISPR-Cas systems, probiotics, and combination therapies
- Evaluation of alternative approaches to combat both emergence and persistence of resistance

Behavioural and Social Research

- Understanding decision-making processes among farmers, veterinarians, and other stakeholders regarding antimicrobial use
- Investigation of the "human factor" in AMR/AMU challenges, including risk perception, social norms, and cultural influences
- Research into effective behaviour change interventions and communication strategies
- Analysis of social and economic barriers to adopting AMR reduction practices
- Evaluation of peer influence, professional networks, and knowledge transfer mechanisms
- Assessment of training needs and educational approaches for different stakeholder groups

IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

Stakeholder engagement

Tools and support for farmers to present cases, addressing hard-to-reach farmers, understanding motivation factors (peer pressure, profit considerations, animal/plant/soil health and welfare concerns).

Communication strategies

role of veterinary prescribing champions, industry council involvement, regulators, politicians, peer support system, competitive benchmarking.

Data management

Data sensitivity issues, need for safe data sharing systems, protection against penalisation, value demonstration for data sharing, competitive advantage concerns.

PRIORITISATION CRITERIA

Structured method

Stakeholder inclusion in priority setting, balance between urgent voices and importance (impact vs importance framework), use of tools like Menti.com for ranking.

Time management

Triage approach, short-medium-long-term planning, output-focused planning, implementation pathways.

CHALLENGES AND MITIGATION

Regulatory framework

Early engagement with regulators, implementation feasibility assessment, vaccine licensing issues (UK-EU alignment needs, resource efficiency in registration).

Education

School-level AMR education, medical professional training, veterinary professional development, food handler awareness.

Emerging challenges (*new pathogens, effectiveness of existing interventions, global AMR influence, trade implications*)

Long-term strategic planning with resource allocation balance, stakeholder engagement maintenance, international collaboration, continuous assessment and adaptation.

IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSLATION

Effectiveness metrics

AMU fluctuation understanding, intervention balance assessment, impact measurement of existing implementations, cost-benefit analysis. Unintended consequences. Environmental impact, economic implications, animal and plant health and welfare effects, trade relationship impacts.

Science to Practice

Early stakeholder engagement, practical tool development, easy recording systems, accessible information sharing

Communication challenges

Addressing sensationalist reporting, promoting positive stories, science-based communication, managing public perception.

APPENDIX 4 - EXPANDING THE NETWORK

PRIMARY STAKEHOLDERS IDENTIFIED

Farmers and Veterinarians - Direct engagement needed: on-farm visits and consultations, presence at farming shows, individual approach to different farmers groups, focus on practicing vets rather than just academic vets, use of Veterinary Champions as advocates (Farm Vet Champions programme led by Fiona Lovatt). Gwen Rees of Arwain DGC in Wales would be a valuable connection.

Youth Engagement – focus on future change-maker - Young farmers federations and association like Young Vet Network, but also educational institutions (HND, HNC, BScs programmes).

Industry Organisations:

- Professional organisations: National Farmers Union, British Poultry Council, RUMA, Red Tractor, Soil Association, RSPCA/SSPCA, Farmer's Union of Wales
- Food industry: retailers and processors, Food and Drink Federation, Chilled Food Association, Fresh Produce Consortium, alternative protein producers, FAIRR initiative (investor consortium)

Government and Regulatory Engagement

- Regulatory bodies such as Veterinary Medicines Directorate, CEFAS, FSS, FSA, FSA-NI, Environment Agencies (across all four nations), APHA, UKHSA.
- Advisory Committee on the Microbiological Safety of Food.
- Parliamentary connections like House of Lords members (Minette Batters, Sandy Trees, Baroness Natalie Bennett who works on AMR and is interested in biocides and pesticides) and House of Commons members (Danny Chambers), policy makers, government departments.

Media and Public Relations

- Targeted approach: engagement with friendly journalists, celebrity ambassadors (noting that careful management would be needed), The Conversation articles, farming press (Farmer's Weekly, Farmer's Guardian, Vet Times, Farming Monthly, UK-VET Livestock, BVA – Vet Record, RCVS Knowledge)
- Communication tools: newsletters/quarterly bulletins, social media, podcasts, personal stories and case studies, accessible language, agricultural show presence

International Dimension

- Learning from other nations, international organisations and food producing countries, Balance needed between local and global focus
- Challenges: restrictions on international partner inclusion, coordination of global reduction efforts, cross-border implementation issues

Specialised Sectors and Groups

- Environmental focus: water utilities, environmental groups, soil associations, National Trust
- Technical focus: EcoLab, Campden BRI (phage work), STFCFood+ Network, implementation scientist

Non-Traditional or Novel Stakeholders

- Religious organisations (Church of England/Wales, Scotland agricultural officers)
- Cultural representatives: regional food specialists, cultural food producers, farming and vet union representation
- Alternative protein producers
- Insect protein developers
- Cultured food manufacturers

IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY - PRACTICAL APPROACHES

- Flexible funding for short-term exchanges/engagement
- Field trips to different facilities
- Regular stakeholder meetings
- Knowledge transfer activities
- Consider impacts over different timescales and who we want to impact – 5 years, 10 years etc

ALIGNMENT WITH EXISTING INITIATIVES

Network integration

Scoping exercise with other networks, overlap avoidance, activity alignment, cross-network collaboration.

Highlight uniqueness and integration

Clear messaging, defined direction, regular publication outputs, consistent stakeholder updates.

THE AMAST NETWORK

AntiMicrobial Resistance in Agrifood Systems Transdisciplinary Network

A UKRI NETWORK

UK Research
and Innovation

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